

A New Era for Pharmaceutical Development: Artificial Intelligence Powered Drug Discovery

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Abstract. Artificial intelligence (AI) is rapidly transforming the drug discovery process. AI algorithms can be used to analyze large and complex datasets, identify new drug targets and drug candidates, and predict the efficacy and safety of drug candidates. This has the potential to significantly accelerate the development of new drugs and bring them to market more quickly. The purpose of writing this review article on AI in drug discovery is multifaceted and to provide readers with a comprehensive understanding of how AI is reshaping the pharmaceutical industry, including their applications, benefits, and challenges. To showcase the innovative approaches and technologies that are driving advancements in drug discovery, emphasizing the role of AI as catalysts for change. To present real-world examples of successful applications of AI in pharmaceutical industry, demonstrating their impact and potential. Ultimately, the purpose of writing this review article is to share knowledge, promote innovation, and contribute to the ongoing dialogue surrounding the use of AI in drug development, with the goal of improving healthcare and advancing pharmaceutical research.

Keywords: Drug discovery, Health care, Pharmaceutical research

1. Introduction

1.1. The importance of drug discovery:-

A novel therapeutic molecule's introduction into clinical practice is the process of drug discovery in its broadest sense. It covers each stage, from early fundamental research to pinpoint a viable molecular target to demanding Phase III clinical trials to support the drug's commercial launch to post-market pharmacosurveillance and drug repurposing studies. Chemical entities that have the potential to be therapeutic agents must be recognized and thoroughly explored during the protracted and expensive drug development process. An estimated billions of dollars and more than 10 years of labor go into developing each new drug that is put on the market [1-3] which is depicted in figure1. Therefore, there is great interest in methods that can quicken and facilitate the drug development process.

Figure.1.Traditional drug discovery which is a time consuming and expensive method

1.2.The role of AI in accelerating drug discovery

Artificial intelligence has become an important player in creating novel treatments for a variety of ailments in recent years[4-6]. Forbes claims that by employing AI for drug research, pharmaceutical companies can save up to 70% of their costs. Drug discovery is often a labor- and time-intensive procedure[7-16]. Due to the intricacy of the human immune system, it involves a number of phases from target identification through clinical trials.AI has the ability to speed up drug discovery, cut expenses and time spent on it, and result in the creation of more potent and effective therapies.

2. AI Tools in Drug Discovery:

There are a variety of tools used in AI for drug discovery out of which few important tools and their applications are shown in the following Table.1.

S.no	Name of AI Tool	Application
1	Machine learning (ML) algorithms	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To train AI models to identify patterns and make predictions. Used in drug discovery include support vector machines (SVMs), random forests, and neural networks.
2	Deep learning (DL) algorithms	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To learn from large amounts of data without being explicitly programmed. Well-suited for drug discovery tasks such as image analysis and protein structure prediction.
3	Natural language processing (NLP) algorithms	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To extract meaning from text. To analyze large datasets of biomedical literature to identify new drug targets and drug candidates.
4	Computer-aided drug design (CADD) software	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To design and simulate new drug molecules. To identify drug molecules that are likely to bind to their targets and have fewer side effects.
5	High-performance computing (HPC) systems	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To train and run AI models. For processing the large amounts of data that are required to train AI models for drug discovery tasks.

Here are some examples of specific AI tools that are used in drug discovery:

Atomwise: Atomwise is a company that provides AI-powered drug discovery tools. Atomwise's AI platform can be used to screen large libraries of potential drug candidates and to predict their efficacy and safety[9-10].

BenevolentAI: BenevolentAI is a company that provides AI-powered drug discovery tools. BenevolentAI's AI platform can be used to examine huge biomedical data sets and find new drug targets. and drug candidates[11-12].

Insilico Medicine: Insilico Medicine is a company that provides AI-powered drug discovery tools. Insilico Medicine's AI platform can be used to design and synthesize new drug molecules and to predict their efficacy and safety[13-14].

Exscientia: Exscientia is a company that provides AI-powered drug discovery services. Exscientia uses its AI platform to design and synthesize new drug molecules and to conduct preclinical and clinical trials[15-16].

3.Applications of AI in Drug Discovery:

Here few applications of artificial intelligence in drug discovery are given.

In 2020, GlaxoSmithKline (GSK) and AI startup BenevolentAI used AI to identify a new drug target for Alzheimer's disease. The AI platform analyzed a large dataset of genetic, protein, and other data to identify new targets for Alzheimer's disease treatment. The AI platform identified a target protein called GSK-3, which is known to be involved in the development of Alzheimer's disease. GSK then used AI to design a new drug candidate that targets GSK-3. This drug candidate is currently in clinical trials[17].

Demis Hassabis developed AlphaFold which predicts the 3D structure of proteins with unprecedented accuracy. This breakthrough could revolutionize drug discovery, as it allows scientists to better understand how proteins work and how drugs interact with them. AlphaFold has already been used to identify new drug targets and to design new drug molecules[18].

Abraham Heifets developed the Atomwise AI platform, which can screen millions of potential drug candidates in a matter of hours. This is significantly faster than traditional drug screening methods, which can take months or even years. Atomwise's platform has been used to identify new drug leads for a variety of diseases, including cancer, Alzheimer's disease, and rare diseases.[19].

Hopkins' work on Exscientia's AI platform has the potential to make a significant impact on the healthcare industry. By making it faster, more efficient, and more cost-effective to develop new drugs, Exscientia's AI platform could help to bring new and innovative drugs to market sooner This is significantly faster than traditional drug design methods, which can take years. Exscientia's platform has been used to design and synthesize new drug candidates for a variety of diseases, including cancer, Alzheimer's disease, and infectious diseases[20].

Wong et al. (2023) described Insilico Medicine's AI platform as a "comprehensive and integrated platform that covers all aspects of the drug discovery process, from target identification to lead optimization to clinical trials." The platform uses a variety of AI techniques, including machine learning, deep learning, and natural language processing, to analyze large datasets of biomedical data.. This can help to reduce the risk of failure in clinical trials and to accelerate the development of new drugs. Insilico's platform has been used to predict the safety and efficacy of drug candidates for a variety of diseases, including cancer, Alzheimer's disease, and infectious diseases[21].

3.1. Comparative analysis of some of the leading AI tools used in drug discovery:

After reviewing various articles, comparative analysis of all AI tools are given in the table no.2.

Table.2.

Tool	Strengths	Weaknesses
Atomwise	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Can screen large libraries of potential drug candidates quickly and efficiently. Can predict the efficacy and safety of drug candidates with high accuracy. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Requires large amounts of data to train the AI models. Can be expensive to use.
BenevolentAI	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Can identify new drug targets from large datasets of biomedical data. Can design and synthesize new drug molecules. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Still in its early stages of development. Can be expensive to use.
Insilico Medicine	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Can design and synthesize new drug molecules. Can predict the efficacy and safety of drug candidates in preclinical and clinical trials. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Still in its early stages of development. Can be expensive to use.
Exscientia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Offers a full suite of AI-powered drug discovery services, from target identification to lead optimization to clinical trials. Has a track record of success in developing new drugs. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Can be expensive to use. * Still in its early stages of development.

Overall, all of these AI tools offer significant advantages for drug discovery. However, they also have some limitations, such as the need for large amounts of data and the fact that they are still in their early stages of development.

Here is a table no.3 that summarizes the key features of each tool:

Table.3

Feature	Atomwise	BenevolentAI	Insilico Medicine	Exscientia
Target identification	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Drug design	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Virtual screening	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Preclinical testing	Yes	No	Yes	Yes
Clinical trials	No	No	No	Yes

From this analysis it is observed that Exscientia is the only tool that offers a full suite of AI-powered drug discovery services, from target identification to clinical trials. This makes it a good option for companies that are looking for a one-stop shop for AI-powered drug discovery. The other tools are more specialized, but they can still be very useful for specific tasks. For example, Atomwise is a good option for companies that need to screen large libraries of potential drug candidates quickly and efficiently. BenevolentAI is a good option for companies that need to identify new drug targets or design new drug molecules. Insilico Medicine is a good option for companies that need to predict the efficacy and safety of drug candidates in preclinical and clinical trials. Ultimately, the best AI tool for drug discovery will depend on the specific needs of the company.

4. Challenges and Limitations:

AI has the potential to revolutionize drug discovery, but there are challenges to be addressed first. These challenges include the need for high-quality data, the interpretability of AI models, and ethical concerns. Despite these challenges, AI has the potential to make a significant impact on drug discovery by automating tasks, identifying new drug targets and drug candidates, and predicting the efficacy and safety of drug candidates. [22-25].

5. Conclusion:

AI is transforming drug discovery, automating tasks, streamlining processes, and enabling new approaches. AI-driven virtual screening and drug design allow scientists to efficiently identify and develop new drug molecules. AI-enabled personalized medicine and clinical trials tailor treatments to individual patients and accelerate development. AI is poised to revolutionize drug discovery in the coming years, accelerating the development of new, more effective, and more affordable drugs for a wide range of diseases.

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